

FORMATION OF PERSONALITY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE POTENTIAL OF HIGH SCHOOL STUDENTS WITH THE USE OF FITNESS TECHNOLOGIES.

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Annotation: This article discusses the features of high school students as a social group, their value-semantic orientations in modern society. The possibility of developing a harmonious developed personality by means of fitness technologies using innovative techniques and methods when performing exercises is highlighted. Theoretical foundations of fitness as a technology of physical culture in high school, as well as an integrated approach to the improvement and development of the body are analyzed.

Keywords: fitness, youth, state youth policy, value-semantic orientations, monitoring of physical parameters, proper nutrition, systematic monitoring

Today, in our country, health-improving physical culture has developed enormously, namely, fitness and the related need of modern society to develop its physical potential, the desire for health, well-being.

Fitness is inextricably linked with physical culture and the general culture of a person. By doing fitness, high school students not only develop and improve their physical abilities, but also form other personal qualities - moral and ethical.

Special exercise techniques can be used in various training programs. They help to achieve the best results in physical education classes and increase student motivation.

Monitoring the physical parameters of students using devices that allow you to control the pulse, blood pressure, body temperature and other indicators.

Monitoring the physical parameters of students using special devices is an important tool for assessing the effectiveness of classes and monitoring the health of students. The following equipment can be used to monitor the pulse and other indicators:

1. Heart rate monitors are devices that record the heart rate during exercise. They can be worn on the wrist or chest and transmit data in real time to a special monitor or smartphone.

2. Blood oxygen measuring devices - they allow you to assess the level of oxygen in the blood during exercise and evaluate the degree of aerobic endurance.

3. Blood pressure measuring devices - they allow you to monitor blood pressure during exercise and assess the risk of cardiovascular diseases.

4. Thermometers - to monitor body temperature before, during and after exercise [1].

Such devices not only allow you to monitor the health of students, but also help monitor the effectiveness of training. The use of these devices can reduce the risk of injury and muscle strain, allow you to better regulate the load and achieve better results. In addition, the data obtained can be used to develop personal training programs and more effectively work with students, taking into account their individual characteristics and needs.

5. Application of additional vital skills, such as proper nutrition, sleep, body hygiene. Proper nutrition, sufficient sleep and body hygiene are the main vital skills that must be applied to achieve a healthy lifestyle. They will be useful for both students and teachers to have more energy and better assimilate information at school.

Nutrition is one of the main factors of health. Proper nutrition not only maintains health, but also improves physical fitness, helps to lose excess weight and prevents many diseases. School programs can include courses on proper nutrition, which will help children understand what foods to eat to get the maximum benefits for health and fitness. Teachers can also encourage healthy eating in school cafeterias, providing students with healthy snacks and drinks.

Sleep is another important factor for human health. Adequate sleep helps students maintain concentration during the day, improves memory, and allows them to study more effectively. Teachers can encourage proper sleep patterns in students by promoting the need for late bedtimes and a regular daily routine.

Hygiene is a key aspect of a healthy lifestyle, which includes regular hand washing, dental care, and showering. Schools should promote hygiene rules and ensure that students follow them. This will reduce the risk of contracting many infectious diseases. The use of all these skills helps to form a healthy lifestyle in students and teachers, which is essential for effective learning.

The content of the concept of "fitness technologies" in physical education lessons may include:

1. An integrated approach to the health and development of students' bodies [2].

An integrated approach to the health and development of students' bodies involves the use of various methods and means to achieve better results. It includes a set of activities aimed at developing the physical and emotional health of students.

Physical health is a key component of a comprehensive approach to student health. School programs should include physical education and sports clubs. This helps improve physical fitness, increase performance and stress resistance, and strengthen the immune system. In addition, sports can help students develop as individuals and acquire important life skills such as persistence, discipline, and resistance to pressure.

As part of a comprehensive approach, health promotion classes such as yoga, pilates, and dancing should be held. These areas help improve posture, flexibility, coordination of movements, reduce the risk of developing musculoskeletal diseases, and strengthen the cardiovascular system.

4. Emphasis on the importance of instilling a healthy lifestyle and increasing student motivation in physical education classes [4].

Emphasis on the importance of instilling a healthy lifestyle and increasing student motivation in physical education classes is of great importance in the educational process. A healthy lifestyle includes a number of factors, such as healthy eating, physical activity, giving up bad habits and avoiding stress. Physical education is one of the most important elements of a healthy lifestyle, as it helps to strengthen health and improve physical fitness.

Increasing the motivation of students in physical education classes can be achieved by increasing interest in classes, including new elements in the programs, organizing competitions between students and creating a friendly atmosphere in groups.

One way to increase the motivation of students is to include elements of play in the process of physical education classes. This can be holding classes outdoors, playing team sports, etc. It is also important to organize joint events with other subjects, such as biology, anatomy and physiology, so that students can better understand what effect physical activity has on their body.

Instilling a healthy lifestyle should begin in childhood. To maintain children's interest in physical education classes, it is necessary to use modern methods that will correspond to the interests and needs of children and will contribute to the development of their athletic potential. Various healthy lifestyle programs implemented in schools provide students with the opportunity to receive up-to-date information on the topic, which also contributes to the formation of healthy habits. In general, emphasizing the importance of a healthy lifestyle and increasing the motivation of students in physical education classes is an important component of the educational

process, which contributes to improving the health and physical fitness of students.

Pay special attention to developing the correct technique for performing exercises and adjusting it during classes[Developing the correct technique for performing exercises is one of the main areas of physical education. Correctly performed exercises help to avoid injuries, increase the effectiveness of training, and make classes more enjoyable and comfortable.

During physical education classes, teachers should pay special attention to developing the correct technique for performing exercises and adjusting it during classes. At the beginning of the course, teachers should show students how to perform each exercise correctly, paying attention to the correct positioning of the body and movements, and then monitor the technique during classes.

In addition, it is necessary to pay attention to such factors as the choice of equipment and loads used when performing exercises. Effective technique will not be achieved with the wrong selection of equipment and loads. Therefore, the optimal choice of loads and equipment is also an important element in developing the correct technique for performing exercises.

In general, developing the correct technique for performing exercises is an important skill for those involved in physical education. Teachers should pay special attention to this aspect in order to teach students the correct technique and prevent possible injuries and damage. The concept of "fitness technology" in physical education classes includes complex methods and means aimed at effective and safe training of students, as well as increasing motivation and improving the health of the body.

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